

INTERLAMINAR DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS AND STRENGTH OF 3-D ORTHOGONAL INTERLOCKED FABRIC COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were executed for interlaminar fracture toughness of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite. The jagged load-deflection curves caused by unstable crack propagation were obtained. The strain energy release rate for 3-D composite becomes far higher even if the volume fraction of z-direction fiber is small, and becomes higher as the volume fraction becomes high. The observation of the specimens revealed that z-direction fibers made the fracture more complex and caused many characteristic phenomena: debondings of the z-direction fiber from in-plane layer; its failure or pull-out and bridging of z-direction fiber; crack branching, deviation and secondary crack almost in front of the crack tip. They may increase the absorbed fracture energy. The double-notched shear (DNS) tests were carried out to estimate the interlaminar shear strength of the present composite. The shear strength were nearly equal for different distance between the notches at least for tested cases.

KEYWORDS: 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite, tabbed DCB test, DNS test, mode I strain energy release rate, fiber bridging

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite materials have many advantages and are frequently used in many kinds of fields [1], but most of them are two-dimensional (2-D) laminated composites, so interlaminar delamination is the weakest failure mode in these materials. In fact, the delamination is considered to be the most prevent life-limiting growth mode in composite structures [2]. Various techniques have been introduced to enhance the interlaminar strength. One way is a usage of thermoplastic or toughened thermoset matrices. One of the most effective way is three-dimensional (3-D) fabric construction technique [3], [4] such as braiding, weaving, knitting or stitching process. Among them, the orthogonal interlocked fabric composite provides fiber architecture aimed at retaining in-plane performance while enhancing out-of-plane properties, by including a small amount of through-the-thickness reinforcement [5]. It is important to investigate quantitatively the influence of the z-direction reinforcement on the material performances to assess fully the trade-off study between in-

plane and interlaminar properties in the design of fabric composite structures. Until now, several experimental studies about interlaminar toughness have been done for 3-D fabric composites [6] - [8]. On the other hand, to the authors' knowledge, few analyses have been carried out about the material [9]. The authors modified the model used in Ref. 9 and carried out the analyses [10].

In this paper, two kinds of the experiments related to the interlaminar properties of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite are performed. The DCB tests were executed for Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and the results were compared with those of unidirectional composite. The effect of z-direction fiber bundle on the interlaminar fracture behavior of the material is discussed. From the observation of the specimen after the test, the fracture mechanism of the material is discussed. To estimate the interlaminar shear strength of the 3-D composite, the double-notched shear (DNS) tests were carried out in compression.

EXPERIMENTS

Material Systems and Properties

Fig. 1: Fiber structure of five-axes 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite

The orthogonal interlocked fabric composites used in our experiments were made of CF/Epoxy, which were manufactured in Nagoya Aerospace Systems Division, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Co. Ltd. (MHI). The fiber architecture of 3-D composite used here is given in Figure 1. It was composed of five axes fiber yarns: four of them were in-plane and the other was z-direction. To fabricate the composites, resin transfer molding (RTM) process was adopted. The stacking sequence was $[\pm 45/0/90]_{3S}$ thus the total number of plies is 24. Detailed data of the properties of 3-D composite used here is given in Table 1. Carbon fiber TR40 was used for in-plane fiber in all the specimens. There were three types of the specimens: C1 and C2 were reinforced in z-direction by carbon fiber TR40 and K is reinforced in z-direction by aramid fiber K49. The z-direction fiber tows were 1K or 3K, respectively in C1 and C2, thus volume fraction of fibers running in the z-direction was different. The unidirectional composite with heat resistant thermoplastic resin, CF/PI-SP, was also tested as a reference. The properties of PI-SP are as follows: $T_g = 254$ [°C], the tensile strength = 91.2 [MPa] and the tensile modulus = 2.65 [GPa].

Table 1: Properties of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite

Type		C1	C2	K
fibers	in-plane z-direction	TR40 - 1K	TR40 - 12K (carbon fiber) TR40 - 3K	K49 - 768
distance between z-fibers [mm]			3.9 $\overset{\sim}{\sim}$ 3.9	
fiber volume fraction [%]	total	54.2	54.7	54.5
	0°	20.6	20.4	20.5
	- 45°	29.2	28.9	29.0
	+45°	29.2	28.9	29.0
	90°	20.6	20.4	20.5
	z-direction	0.5	1.4	1.1

Testing Procedure for DCB Test

Fig. 2: Geometry of tabbed DCB specimen

The DCB test is a common method for Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. This method has been applied to 2-D composite laminate successfully. However classical DCB specimen cannot be used in the test for 3-D composites. Because this material has high interlaminar strength, usually it fails first at the root of the DCB beam by a bending moment with no interlaminar fracture toughness data. To avoid this difficulty, several methods have been contrived recently. For example, Guenon *et al.* developed one method by using the tabbed DCB specimen [5]. Another test method developed in National Aerospace Laboratory by Ishikawa *et al.* [7].

Fig. 3: Test configuration of tabbed DCB specimen

Figure 2 shows the specimen design and dimensions used in this study, which have been developed by Ishikawa *et al.* This specimen is cut out to insert the jig useful when the load to extend the delamination is high. Figure 3 shows the feature of the specimen using unidirectional CFRP tab. Initial crack was given in this specimen artificially by machining. The width of the specimen was measured at three points and initial artificial crack length was measured on both sides. The DCB specimen was loaded in tension by the INSTRON 4502 screw-driven testing machine in a displacement-controlled mode with 0.25 [mm/min] cross-head speed.

Figure 4 illustrates the schematic load-deflection curve for the present 3-D composite. The specimen was loaded till the load decreased suddenly at the point A, then the machine was stopped to measure the crack length. For the current 3-D composites, it is uncertain whether

Fig. 4: Schematic load-deflection curve of 3-D composite

the geometry of crack is similar to that of initial states or not. Therefore, the crack length was measured on both sides and the averaged value was employed. This average was used in calculation of the strain energy release rate, G_I , under the assumption of a straight tip line. The curve of load versus crack opening displacement, which is assumed to be identical with cross head displacement, had been plotted during the experiment. After the experiment, loads and opening displacements at the instances when the load suddenly dropped were picked up. With these data, G_I was calculated by the area method, which is based on energy consideration and suitable to estimate it for the 3-D composites. The first load drop point was neglected and other data after the second drop were utilized to calculate G_I because the first drop is affected by a dull artificial crack tip.

Testing Procedure for Shear Tests

The interlaminar shear strength was evaluated with the DNS tests. The geometry of the specimen is shown in Figure 5. The specimen has two alternate notches with interval of L whose depths are half of the thickness of the specimen. Restricting the thickness-wise deformation, the specimen was compressed up to failure between the notches by the INSTRON 4505 screw-driven testing machine in a displacement-controlled mode with 1.0 [mm/min] cross-head speed. The tests were conducted for two types of the specimen of different distances between the notches 6.4 [mm] and 12.7 [mm].

Fig. 5: Geometry of DNS specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

DCB Tests

The DCB tests were carried out for three types of the materials, namely C1, C2 and K. As for C1 series, five specimens were tested, and three specimens were tested for C2 and K series. As for unidirectional CF/PI-SP composite, six specimens were tested.

Load-Deflection Curve for 3-D Fabric Composite

Figure 6 shows the typical load-deflection curve of C2 series where the cross-head displacement is assumed as the crack opening displacement. Similar curves were obtained for other materials in the tests. At the beginning of loading procedure, the load increases almost linearly, then drops abruptly when the crack extends. The crack extends step by step and unstably in a manner so-called stick-slip behavior. This behavior is presumably ascribed to the existence of the z-direction fiber. The load drops every time when the crack extends, and the load drop step is generally independent of the crack opening displacement. The peak load decreases gradually as the crack extension.

Fig. 6: Typical load-deflection curve for C2 series

Effect of z-direction Fibers

Figure 7 shows the Mode I strain energy release rate G_I , for C1 series as a function of normalized crack growth length. The normalized crack growth length is defined as $(a - a_0) / a_0$, where a is an instant crack length and a_0 is an initial crack length. The averaged values of G_I for all the specimens are listed in Table 2. The values for #1 and #2 are distributed in a narrow region, from 0.69 [kN/m] to 1.54 [kN/m] for #1 and from 0.75 [kN/m] to 1.54 [kN/m] for #2. The averaged values for #1 and #2 are 0.99 [kN/m] and 1.33 [kN/m], respectively, as listed in Table 2. On the other hand, the values of G_I for #3, #4 and #5 are distributed widely, for example, from 0.45 [kN/m] to 4.73 [kN/m] for #5. Most values for these three specimens are higher than those for #1 and #2, with the higher average of 1.42 [kN/m] for #3, 1.86 [kN/m] for #4 and 1.55 [kN/m] for #5. On the whole, the G_I values remain in particular region from 0.8 [kN/m] to 2.0 [kN/m] with a few exception, exhibiting the average for C1 series of 1.43 [kN/m].

Fig. 7: Strain energy release rate for C1 series as a function of normalized crack growth length

Table 2: Strain energy release rate of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite

Strain energy release rate [kN/m]						
Type	Specimen					average
	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	
C1	0.99	1.33	1.42	1.86	1.55	1.43
C2	6.18	4.95	3.79			4.98
K	3.43	2.75	3.25			3.14

The averaged strain energy release rates of unidirectional CF/PI-SP for all the specimens are listed in Table 3. The values are nearly constant with the average of the whole values of 0.64 [kN/m], which is considerably lower than that of C1 series. In Ref. 11, it was reported that G_I for conventional unidirectional CF/Epoxy composite was 0.094 [kN/m] and that for unidirectional CF/PEEK composite was 1.82 [kN/m]. Comparing with these results, the value of G_I for C1 series is high enough, although this composite system with normal epoxy resin contains only 0.5% of z-direction fibers.

Table 3: Strain energy release rate of unidirectional CF/PI-SP composite

Strain energy release rate [kN/m]						
Specimen						average
#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	
0.53	0.62	0.68	0.63	0.70	0.66	0.64

Effect of the Volume Fraction of z-direction Fibers

Fig. 8: Strain energy release rate for C2 series as a function of normalized crack growth length

Figure 8 shows the G_I for C2 series as a function of normalized crack growth length and their average are also listed in Table 2. The values of G_I for #1 and #2 are distributed widely, from 1.23 [kN/m] to 16.36 [kN/m] for #1 and from 0.99 [kN/m] to 10.22 [kN/m] for #2 with the average for #1 and #2 being 6.18 [kN/m] and 4.95 [kN/m], respectively. In the case of #3, G_I are distributed in a narrow region, from 3.23 [kN/m] to 5.14 [kN/m] with 3.79 [kN/m] in average. The averaged value for whole C2 series is obtained as 4.98 [kN/m]. Figure 9 shows the results for K series as a function of normalized crack growth length. The averaged values for each specimen are 3.43 [kN/m] for #1, 2.75 [kN/m] for #2 and 3.25 [kN/m] for #3 with the whole average of 3.14 [kN/m], as listed in Table 2. Note that the values of G_I for each specimen disperse widely again, for example, from 0.33 [kN/m] to 7.83 [kN/m] for #3. A tendency that G_I becomes high with crack growth is observed.

Fig. 9: Strain energy release rate for K series as a function of normalized crack growth length

In summary, the whole average are 1.43 [kN/m] for C1, 4.98 [kN/m] for C2 and 3.14 [kN/m] for K, respectively, as listed in Table 2. To compare with one another, it is considered that the strain energy release rate and its scatter become more serious as the volume fraction of z-fiber yarn becomes higher.

Fracture Mechanisms in 3-D Composite

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10: Typical failure modes of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite after DCB test: (a) C1 series, and (b) C2 series

As stated earlier, the crack propagated in an unstable stick-slip manner. Stable crack propagation in the matrix was seldom observed. Figure 10(a) shows the photograph of the typical fracture mode in C1 series after the DCB test. The lines seen on the side were written in 1 [cm] distance by pencil for an assistance of crack length measurement. Although AE data were also acquired by a sensor as shown in this photograph, they would not be discussed here. Nevertheless many fracture behavior such as z-fiber bridging and pull-out, crack branching and deviations were observed in this specimen, they were not significant in

comparison with C2. The in-plane fiber bridging and pull-out were also observed. Figure 10(b) shows the photograph of the typical fracture mode in C2 series where it is indicated that the secondary cracks were created and they generally ran parallel to the main crack. The z-fiber bridging and pull-out were prominently observed in this specimen. In addition, failure in most z-direction fibers did not occur in the plane of crack propagation but occurred in the region near the surface where a stress concentration could be expected in the manufacturing process. Based on comparison of the fracture mode between C1 and C2, it is clearly understood that the mechanisms of fracture becomes more complex as z-fiber volume fraction increases. While the load supported by the z-direction fiber increases as z-fiber volume fraction increases, the crack deviation or branching become serious because of the existence of z-fiber.

From these observations, various kinds of fracture phenomena could be found in 3-D composite toughness tests: debondings of z-direction fiber from in plane layers; its failure or pull-out, and bridging by z-direction fiber; crack branching, deviation and secondary crack almost everywhere in front of the crack tip. In addition, the crack branching and deviation may lead to bridging by in-plane fibers. Because these phenomena can be considered to increase the absorbed fracture energy, the crack propagation is apt to be arrested.

Interlaminar Shear Tests

Fig. 11: Typical fracture modes of 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite after the DNS tests

The short beam shear (SBS) test in three-point bending is often used as a simple and convenient method. Although these tests were carried out, the results exhibited serious dependency on the distance between the supporting points. Therefore, the interlaminar shear strength was evaluated with the DNS tests in compression. These tests were carried out only for C2 series specimens by two types of the distances between the notches, 6.4 [mm]: A and 12.7 [mm]: B. The number of specimens was five for each type. The interlaminar shear strength for Type A and Type B were distributed from 86.85 [MPa] to 114.22 [MPa] for Type A and from 92.34 [MPa] to 102.21 [MPa] for Type B. The pitch of z-direction fibers is 3.9 [mm] in the present composite, thus only one or two z-fiber exist between the notches for Type A, while there are three or four z-fibers between the notches for Type B. Therefore, the interlaminar shear strength obtained with Type A depends on the state of the specimen and its scatter becomes serious. On the other hand, the results of Type B exhibit lower scatter than those of Type A. The interlaminar shear strength average were 99.80 [MPa] for Type A and

97.13 [MPa] for Type B with only 2.7% difference between them, although their scatter level were different each other. Therefore, no dependency of the interlaminar shear strength on the distance between the notches was found so far as tested. Figure 11 shows the failure mode of type B after the tests. Only single delamination was observed between the notches along 0° axis fiber yarn, which could be regarded as the result of almost pure-shear fracture.

CONCLUSIONS

The interlaminar fracture toughness and strength of the 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric CF/Epoxy were evaluated by using the tabbed DCB specimen and the interlaminar shear tests. The area method was used in calculation of the strain energy release rate. The interlaminar shear tests were carried out with the DNS test in compression. The conclusions are given as follows:

- 1) The DCB tests were carried out for C1, C2 and K series with the volume fractions of z-direction fiber being 0.5% for C1, 1.4% for C2 and 1.1% for K. The obtained strain energy release rate averages were 1.43 [kJ/m²] for C1, 4.98 [kJ/m²] for C2 and 3.14 [kJ/m²] for K, respectively.
- 2) The value of the strain energy release rate for 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composites was compared with those for tougher unidirectional composites. Although the volume fraction of z-direction fiber is only 0.5%, the strain energy release rate of 3-D CF/Epoxy is fifteen-fold greater than that of the UD composite of similar resin without z-direction reinforcements.
- 3) The difference of the strain energy release rate due to the difference of z-fiber volume fraction was also discussed. The strain energy release rate comes to higher as the z-fiber increases. Moreover, serious scatter was found in the results of the strain energy release rate, and the scatter became more serious with increasing the volume fraction of z-direction fiber.
- 4) The load-deflection curves of 3-D composite were much different from those of unidirectional composites. The jagged curve was obtained for 3-D due to unstable stick-slip crack propagation.
- 5) During and after the DCB tests, the interlaminar crack propagation processes were observed and fracture mechanisms were contemplated. They are far more complicated than those in unidirectional composites. The presence of z-direction fibers causes many characteristic phenomena: debondings of z-direction fiber from in-plane layers; its failure or pull-out, and bridging by z-direction fiber; crack branching, deviation and secondary crack almost everywhere in front of the crack tip. The bridging by in-plane fibers may occur because of the crack branching and deviation. These phenomena increases the absorbed fracture energy and the crack propagation tends to be arrested.
- 6) The interlaminar shear strengths obtained by the SBS test exhibited strong dependency on the distance between the supporting points. On the contrary, those by the DNS tests exhibited almost no dependency on distance between the notches at least for tested cases. It is concluded at present that the DNS test is suitable to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength of the 3-D orthogonal interlocked fabric composite.

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